

Tool 25 – How to make your CS project sustainable

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 5 – sustain) and helps you to reflect about possible actions you can undertake to ensure the outcome, community and financial sustainability of your citizen science (research) project. With the options below you can make sure the results of your CS project are being taken up by academia, policy makers, and other relevant societal actors.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

OUTCOME SUSTAINABILITY	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Scientific publications: You publish the results of your citizen science (research) project in open access publishing, for instance in the peer-reviewed journal ‘Theory and Practice’.	<input type="checkbox"/>
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Broad dissemination towards the general public: Besides disseminating your results within an academic context, it is also important that you publish your results in a comprehensible and accessible way to a broad audience. For instance, you can publish your results in the newspaper, in a popular magazine, participate in a science festival, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Connect with policy makers: The outcomes of your research (project) can be of relevance to ongoing policy debates if the project has a high political or societal prominence. Therefore, it is recommended that you connect with policy makers from the start of your research project and raise awareness about your activities. At the end of the project, you can formulate specific guidelines which can feed into the policy debate. For instance, you can formulate guidelines through a policy brief, organise policy workshops, or showcase how your data sets can be of effective usage for long-term monitoring and evaluation of policies.	<input type="checkbox"/>
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Educational outreach: During or at the end of your research (project), you can opt to translate the outcomes into educational materials. These educational materials can be disseminated through formal and informal learning networks. For instance, you can develop an educational package, cardboard games, quizzes, card sets, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>

FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY

- **Subsequent funding:** Once your project is finished, you can apply for other (larger) funding opportunities at national and international level. For instance, you can apply for funding in the Horizon Europe programme.
- **Generate revenue:** If your citizen science (research) project has a commercial objective, then you can launch any type of hardware or software into the market as a service. Even if you publish the code with open access, you can still charge for tailored features, specific improvements, training, etc. Be sure to check the intellectual property rights. For instance, you can provide advice to external stakeholders on how to set up a citizen science tool, or you can charge for specific customized features.
- **Spin-off:** In a commercial spirit, you can decide to start a spin-off. Spin-offs are start-up companies whose main activities are based on the formal transfer of research results originating from a university. For instance, you can decide to commercialize a mobile application or sensor for citizen engagement.